

D5.5

Test Evaluation Report

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N. 953432.

The content of this deliverable does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the author(s).

WP5 Test and Evaluation

D5.5 Test Evaluation Report

Contract number:	953432
Project acronym:	FitDrive
Project title:	Monitoring Devices for Overall Fitness of Drivers
Planned delivery date:	M41 (Jan 2025)
Leading partner:	UNISAP
Partners contributed:	MDU AIPSS ITCL
Document date:	21/03/2025
Version:	3
Subversion:	2
Deliverable type:	Report
Remarks:	
Status:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> PU (Public) <input type="radio"/> PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services) <input type="radio"/> Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) (please specify the group) <input type="radio"/> Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document Revision Log

Version	Subversion	Date	Description	Author
1	0	07/02/2025	Deliverable Draft	Andrea Giorgi, UNISAP
1	1	18/02/2025	Integration of contents	Gianluca Di Flumeri, UNISAP
2	0	14/03/2025	Version for internal review	Gianluca Di Flumeri, UNISAP
2	1	15/03/2025	Internal review	Mir Riyanul Islam, MDU
2	2	17/03/2025	Internal review	Carlo Polidori, AIPSS
2	3	17/03/2025	Internal review	Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, MDU
2	4	19/03/2025	Internal review & formatting	Marteyn van Gasteren, ITCL
3	0	20/03/2025	Updated version after reviews	Andrea Giorgi, Gianluca Di Flumeri, UNISAP
3	1	20/03/2025	Final checks	Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Mir Riyanul Islam, MDU
3	2	21/03/2025	Final review and formatting	Marteyn van Gasteren, ITCL

Executive Summary

The present deliverable is one of the outputs of the T5.4 (Test Evaluation) and it is aimed at providing a comprehensive overview of the different steps of the FitDrive project, with respect to the project objectives, and providing evidence of the main results achieved in terms of research and development activities. In this document, the focus is the logical link between the experimental activities (Cycles) and their role with respect to the overall project objective, therefore please refer to project deliverables for further details regarding the rationale, design, and results of single experimental Cycles.

The FitDrive project was organized into four distinct experimental pilot cycles, named C1 to C4, designed to conceptualize, develop, and validate an innovative system for monitoring drivers' fitness levels, with regards to fatigue. The primary objective was to establish a user-centred framework that can detect early indicators of fatigue and proactively alert drivers, thereby improving road safety and promoting drivers' working safety. The FitDrive approach has been characterized by a multidisciplinary methodology, combining the most advanced state-of-the-art knowledge in two key areas: 1) neurophysiological characterization of fatigue, and 2) advanced techniques in data science to develop both generalized and personalized models by combining heterogeneous data. Adopting cutting-edge methodologies, the innovation brought by FitDrive project consisted of using an objective benchmark to detect fatigue to study the resulting psycho-behavioural "configuration" of the fatigued state. This represents an advancement of existing fatigue detection systems, which are currently based only on the "time-on-task" assumption, disregarding any inter-individual and intra-individual variability.

This deliverable focuses on the design and outcomes of the FitDrive project, specifically emphasizing the neurophysiology and data science methodologies employed to collect and analyse the necessary data for building the user-centred monitoring framework. The report provides descriptions of each experimental cycle (C1, C2, C3, and C4), highlighting the specific aims and outputs associated with each phase.

Additionally, the report describes the deviations from the original experimental plan, documenting the challenges encountered during the project and the mitigation and corrective actions implemented to address these issues. This comprehensive overview ensures transparency and offers insights into the iterative development process that underpins the FitDrive system.

The present deliverable is organized in four sections:

- Chapter 1 introduces the FitDrive approach in investigating mental fatigue while driving, highlighting its positioning beyond the state of art. A general overview of the project is given, with a glance at each Cycles and their experimental meaning.
- Chapter 2 describes the single experimental Cycles. For each phase, a brief explanation of its aim is provided, with references to specific Deliverables describing rationale and implementation. Description and meaning of main KPIs and their adoption along the FitDrive project are provided for each phase.

- Chapter 3 discusses the obtained results, evaluating the test procedures with respect to the initial objectives and the overall FitDrive vision.
- Chapter 4 summarizes the challenges faced in performing experimental phases and in implementing the needed feature in the FitDrive framework. For each challenge/issue, countermeasures are listed.
- Chapter 5 concludes the deliverable by suggesting the next implementations needed to improve road safety and allow a deep understanding of impaired driving causes.

1. Contents

1. Contents	6
2. Introduction	9
2.1. State of the art	9
2.2. FitDrive vision	11
3. Test Cycles Description	13
3.1. Cycle C1 – Simulated Driving.....	13
3.2. Cycle C2 – Controlled Driving	16
3.3. Cycle C3 – Individual Profiling.....	18
3.4. Cycle C4 – FitDrive Framework Test.....	20
4. Discussions	23
5. Challenges & Limitations	24
6. Conclusions	25
7. Bibliography	26

List of Figures

Figure 1: Overview of the FitDrive approach and of its experimental cycles, with the used technologies and the final outcomes..... 12

Figure 2: Experimental setup during the simulated driving performed for C1 experiments. On the left, is a picture from the experiments performed in Italy involving van drivers. On the right, is a picture from experiments performed in Spain involving truck drivers. 14

Figure 3: Experimental setup during the realistic driving performed for C2 experiments. On the left, a picture from the experiments performed in Italy involving van drivers. On the right, a picture from experiments performed in Spain involving truck drivers. 16

Figure 4: Driving pattern of a participant driver in C3.1 tests during evening on a single day and a road segment with 100 km/h speed limit. The red dots identified the segments recognized as “unusual” driving style. The average speed was not different from the speed generally adopted by the same driver on that segment, demonstrating that the “unusual” classification was not due to other external variables (e.g. traffic jam) but likely to an altered driving style. This picture is taken from D3.2..... 19

List of Tables

Table 1: List of neurophysiological and behavioural parameters sensitive to fatigue as highlighted during simulated driving (C1). 15

Table 2: List of environmental parameters sensitive to fatigue as highlighted during simulated driving (C1). 15

Table 3: List of vehicular parameters ranking based on their sensitivity to fatigue as highlighted during simulated driving in Italy (C1.1) and Spain (C1.2), in a decreasing order of relevance (top 5). 15

Table 4: List of neurophysiological parameters sensitive to fatigue as highlighted during realistic driving (C2). 17

Table 5: List of vehicular parameters sensitive to fatigue as highlighted during simulated driving in Italy (C2.1) and Spain (C2.2), in a decreasing order of relevance. 18

Table 6: Overview of the classification performance of the FitDrive system in recognizing usual and unusual driving behaviours, and its probable impairment causing deviation from normal behaviour..... 21

Abbreviations

ADAS	Advanced driver-assistance system
Cm[.n]	Pilot cycle m[.n]
EBR	Eyeblink rate
EBD	Eyeblink duration
EBA	Eyeblink amplitude
EEG	Electroencephalography
HR	Heart rate
HRV	Heart rate variability
OBD	On-board diagnostics
SCL	Skin conductance level

2. Introduction

Mental fatigue is a complex, multi-faceted phenomenon that affects cognitive performance, decision-making, and overall driver safety. To recognize its intricate nature, the FitDrive project adopts a multimodal approach to investigating the occurrence of mental fatigue in driving contexts. By integrating diverse data sources and analytical techniques, the project aims to comprehensively understand and address the factors contributing to driver fatigue.

2.1. State of the art

Driver fatigue and drowsiness constitute major risk factors in road safety, contributing to approximately 20% of all road accidents worldwide (SWOV, 2019), even if more in-depth analysis reveals its direct and indirect contribution in up to 50% of accidents (Dawson et al., 2018). In response to this challenge, Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) have incorporated fatigue and drowsiness detection capabilities, but their effectiveness in terms of safety is still a matter of discussion (de Winkel & Christoph, 2025).

Contemporary automotive manufacturers implemented various fatigue detection systems using different technological approaches. The most prominent commercial systems include:

- Mercedes-Benz Attention Assist: Initially introduced in 2009, Attention Assist utilizes a steering angle sensor to establish a driver's baseline steering pattern during the first minutes of driving. The system continuously monitors over 70 parameters, including steering wheel movements, duration of the journey, time of day, and external conditions. When deviations from the baseline pattern are detected, the system issues visual and auditory alerts (*Funzionamento dell'ATTENTION ASSIST con rilevamento dei colpi di sonno | EQS Elettrico Berlina marzo 2022 V297 MBUX | Manuale d'uso e manutenzione, s.d.*).
- Volvo Driver Alert Control (DAC): Volvo's DAC employs a camera that monitors lane markings and analyses vehicle positioning within the lane. The system evaluates steering corrections and lane-keeping behaviour to determine the driver's alertness level (*V40 Driver Alert Control (DAC) | Volvo Support EN-JO, s.d.*). When erratic driving patterns are identified, the system provides graduated warnings to the driver.
- Ford Driver Alert: Ford's system combines camera-based lane-keeping sensors with steering wheel monitoring to detect irregular driving patterns. It analyses micro-corrections in steering and assigns a "drowsiness score" to determine when intervention is necessary (*How do I use the Driver Alert System?, s.d.*).
- Volkswagen Driver Fatigue Detection System (also called Rest Assist): This system integrates multiple data points including steering behaviour, pedal usage, and time factors to identify potential fatigue (Mark, 2017).

Besides these examples, almost all the car manufacturers today provide their own system for fatigue detection, driven also by the EU General Safety Regulation (GSR) (EU Regulation 2019/2144) that as from July 2022 classified them as mandatory on-board devices. The current fatigue detection systems primarily rely on the following sensing technologies and methodologies (Giorgi et al., 2023):

- Vehicle-Based Measurements: These systems monitor driving performance parameters such as steering wheel movements (small corrections, erratic movements); lane positioning and lane departures; velocity changes and braking patterns; pedal usage patterns. These measurements provide indirect assessment of driver alertness through driving behaviour analysis.
- Vision-Based Systems: More advanced systems incorporate in-cabin cameras to monitor such as eye movements and blinking patterns (PERCLOS - percentage of eyelid closure), head position and nodding movements, facial expressions, gaze direction and attention (Giorgi et al., 2024). Industries providing systems to car manufacturers, like Bosch and Continental, have developed camera systems that track eye movements, blink rate, and head position to identify signs of fatigue (*Driver Fatigue and Distraction Monitoring System - Market, Report Size, Worth, Revenue, Growth, Industry Value, Share 2024*, s.d.).

Despite technological advancements, current fatigue detection systems face several significant limitations. First, most commercial systems are developed using data collected from small, often homogeneous groups of participants under controlled conditions. These limited datasets fail to represent the diverse driving population, cultural differences in driving styles, and varying physiological responses to fatigue (Zhang et al., 2019). This results in algorithms that perform well for certain demographic groups but may be less effective for others.

Secondly, current systems generally apply universal thresholds and detection rules across all drivers, disregarding inter-individual variability in fatigue manifestation. Different drivers exhibit distinct baseline behaviours and unique patterns when experiencing fatigue. The lack of personalization means that systems may be oversensitive for some drivers while failing to detect fatigue in others (Martensson et al., 2018).

Perhaps most critically, existing systems predominantly recognize only pronounced manifestations of fatigue and drowsiness, such as significant lane deviations or prolonged eye closures. These indicators typically appear during advanced stages of fatigue when accident risk is already substantially elevated. Current technologies demonstrate limited sensitivity to early fatigue indicators, such as subtle changes in cognitive processing, micro-sleep episodes, or gradual degradation in attention allocation (Phillips et al., 2017). This delayed detection significantly reduces the preventive potential of these systems.

In conclusion, while current commercial fatigue detection systems represent important steps toward enhancing road safety, significant challenges remain, severely limiting the social impact of these systems.

2.2. FitDrive vision

As described in detail in D5.6, the investigation was systematically organized into four propaedeutic experimental phases, referred to as Cycles 1 through 4 (C1, C2, C3 and C4). Each Cycle was designed to collect specific, targeted information, which was subsequently utilized by the following Cycles to refine and enhance the framework for monitoring drivers' fitness to drive. This sequential structure ensured a progressive build-up of knowledge, facilitating the development of a robust and adaptive monitoring system.

Two primary approaches were employed to address this investigation. First, the neurophysiological characterization of human mental states in operational environments, with a particular focus on mental fatigue, provided objective insights into cognitive and physiological changes during driving. Second, advanced data science methods were leveraged for their effectiveness in integrating and analysing heterogeneous data sources—including physiological, behavioural, and environmental inputs—all related to the phenomenon of mental fatigue.

Neurophysiological and behavioural measures collected during the four cycles have been detailed in deliverable D2.5. In summary, a previously validated brain activity-derived metric (from EEG), the Mental Drowsiness index (Di Flumeri et al., 2022), was adopted to objectively detect periods of highest mental fatigue while participants were engaged in driving tasks. The resulting neurophysiological activations, including ocular activity, heart rate variability, and skin conductance, were used to characterize the fatigued state. Concurrently, driver behaviour was scrutinized through the collection of relevant driving parameters, with the aim of defining a specific configuration of these parameters serving as behavioural indicators of fatigue.

This approach represents an improvement of existing research methods on fatigue. These existing methods consist of considering the last part of a fatigue-inducing driving task as representative of the highest level of fatigue experienced. This approach implies that all the drivers experience fatigue in the same way and at the same time, which is far from being the reality. As a solution to this, the FitDrive project overarching aim is to develop a personalized model to evaluate drivers' fitness to drive. With the adoption of an objective benchmark to detect fatigue, the Mental Drowsiness index, the FitDrive framework would be able to recognize in real time the fatigued state. In addition, the proposed approach takes into consideration the inter-individual variability in fatigue insurgence and manifestation, improving fatigue detection and counteracting strategies. Furthermore, to deeply understand the factors playing a role during the fatigued state, additional information related to facial expressions while driving and environmental factors have been gathered to be used when developing the fatigue models.

The features identified as characteristic of the fatigued state were instrumental in building a predictive model of fatigue. The methods and approaches employed in developing this model are described in detail in deliverables D3.1 and D3.2. This predictive framework forms the

backbone of the FitDrive system, enabling real-time detection and intervention to mitigate the risks associated with driving fatigue.

Figure 1: Overview of the FitDrive approach and of its experimental cycles, with the used technologies and the final outcomes.

Through the four experimental cycles (Figure 1), the FitDrive approach initially focused on defining a generalized model capable of detecting fatigue during driving (C1 and C2). Subsequently, during C3, a new dataset containing users’ daily driving a physiological data was collected to translate the generalized model into user specific fatigue model. This adaptation allowed the model to 1) recognize individual drivers; 2) identify each user's typical driving behaviour; and 3) detect anomalies in driving patterns that may indicate altered states, particularly those associated with mental fatigue and the most common impairing states. During C4, the specificity of the FitDrive framework in recognizing users driving the vehicle, as well as identifying potential causes altering their driving style and/or physiological activation, was verified to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed approach. This personalized strategy enhances the system's accuracy and relevance, ensuring that interventions are tailored to the unique characteristics of each driver.

3. Test Cycles Description

This section provides a short overview of each experimental cycle and of the main outcomes, to appreciate the FitDrive system development along all its stages. For more detailed information, please refer to the project deliverables.

3.1. Cycle C1 – Simulated Driving

The first phase of the FitDrive project, C1, focused on evaluating driver fatigue within a controlled, simulated environment (Figure 2). This phase served as the foundational step in the project's broader aim of developing a user-centred framework for monitoring drivers' fitness to drive. By using a simulated driving environment, critical preliminary data were gathered while ensuring participant safety and maintaining a high level of experimental control. C1 experiments took place both in Italy and Spain, and in order to differentiate the dataset, they were labelled respectively as C1.1 (Italy) and C1.2 (Spain).

The simulated environment was meticulously designed to mirror the real-world conditions that participants would later encounter in the realistic driving tasks of C2.

To comprehensively characterize fatigue, a multimodal data collection approach was employed. The gold-standard measure for evaluating mental states, electroencephalography (EEG), was utilized to objectively detect the periods of highest and lowest fatigue.

In addition to EEG, other physiological measures were collected, including ocular activity, heart rate variability, and skin conductance. These metrics provided insights into the neurophysiological manifestations of fatigue. Concurrently, behavioural data related to both users' psychophysical state and driving performance were also gathered. A camera was used to record the facial expressions of drivers during the driving task. Driving performance was investigated by collecting relevant driving parameters extracted from the simulator software. These include lateral oscillation, steering patterns, and accelerating and braking habits. With the aim of extensively investigating the factors concurring to fatigue occurrence, environmental factors such as temperature, luminosity, and CO₂ concentration were analysed in relation to the fatigue level. This comprehensive data collection strategy allowed for a holistic understanding of how fatigue affects both physiological states and driving behaviour.

The aim of C1 was to collect preliminary data related to fatigued driving in a simulated environment. Conducting this initial phase in a controlled setting allowed us to gather high-quality data while minimizing the risks associated with fatigued driving. This strategy not only ensured participant safety but also provided a robust dataset for identifying key fatigue-related features. This investigation sought to achieve several objectives:

1. Identify relevant physiological, behavioural, and environmental features that characterize fatigue from a large sample of participants (n = 33).

2. Confirm the feasibility of the experimental design and setup to ensure the test performed in simulated conditions could be safely and effectively replicated in a realistic driving environment.

Figure 2: Experimental setup during the simulated driving performed for C1 experiments. On the left, is a picture from the experiments performed in Italy involving van drivers. On the right, is a picture from experiments performed in Spain involving truck drivers.

The preliminary results gathered during C1 tests represent the starting point for C2 tests. In particular, the following outcomes were considered when translating the investigation from a simulated to a realistic/naturalistic setting:

1. Identification of features sensitive to fatigue, providing a baseline for further analysis in subsequent cycles (see Table 1 for a description of selected parameters).
2. Collection of user feedback regarding the driving task, which offered valuable insights into the participants' experiences and the task's ability to induce fatigue.
3. Evaluation of user feedback concerning the technologies employed, ensuring that the tools used for data collection were effective and user-friendly.
4. Insights into the mitigation strategies adopted by drivers to recognize and counteract fatigue, contribute to the development of intervention techniques.

Among the results obtained from the C1 experiments, the identification of parameters sensitive to fatigue represents the primary outcome. These parameters include three key domains: i) neurophysiological activation of drivers during fatigued periods (Table 1); ii) environmental factors that may influence fatigue (Table 2); and iii) driving performance metrics reflecting behavioural changes associated with fatigue (Table 3). Please note that in Table 3, the top ranked parameters sensitive to fatigue are mostly similar to the two cycles C1.1 and C1.2. In C2, these parameters will undergo further investigation and validation in a realistic driving environment. After the confirmation of their sensitivity, these parameters will serve as the foundation for developing a generalized model capable of detecting driver fatigue.

Table 1: List of neurophysiological and behavioural parameters sensitive to fatigue as highlighted during simulated driving (C1).

Neurophysiological Parameters	Description	Fatigue Effect
EBR	Blink frequency	Increase
EBD	Blink duration	Increase
EBA	Blink amplitude	-
HR	Heart rate	Increase
HRV	HR variability	-
SCL	Sweating	-

Table 2: List of environmental parameters sensitive to fatigue as highlighted during simulated driving (C1).

Environmental Parameters	Description	Fatigue Effect
CO ₂	CO ₂ concentration	Increase
Luminosity	Lumen in the driving environment	-
Temperature	Temperature in the driving environment	-

Table 3: List of vehicular parameters ranking based on their sensitivity to fatigue as highlighted during simulated driving in Italy (C1.1) and Spain (C1.2), in a decreasing order of relevance (top 5).

Vehicular Parameters	Rank from C1.1	Rank from C1.2
YawExtSns	1	1
LatVelExtSns	2	3
LongVelExtSns	3	5
Acceleration Pedal	4	2
LatAccelExtSns	5	8

The findings from C1 were instrumental in refining the experimental design and the development of more advanced, user-specific models in subsequent phases. C1 was a critical step in the FitDrive project, laying the groundwork for the subsequent experimental cycles. The data collected and insights gained during this phase were essential for understanding the physiological and behavioural correlates of fatigue and for validating the experimental setup. These outcomes directly influenced the design and objectives of C2, where the focus shifted to applying these findings in a realistic driving environment.

3.2. Cycle C2 – Controlled Driving

Following the foundational work completed during C1, the second phase of the FitDrive project transitioned from a simulated environment to real-world conditions to further validate and refine the framework for monitoring drivers' fitness. C2 focused on realistic driving in controlled scenarios, where participants operated vehicles in real environments that were carefully selected to mirror the conditions of the simulated settings used in C1. Similarly to C1, C2 experiments took place both in Italy and Spain, and in order to differentiate the dataset, they were labelled respectively as C2.1 (Italy) and C2.2 (Spain).

The experimental protocol, data collection methods, and analysis procedures employed during C2 were consistent with those used in C1. This methodological consistency allowed for a direct comparison of data across both phases, providing insights into the reliability and applicability of findings from the simulated environment to real-world driving conditions. As in C1, brain activity (EEG) served as the gold-standard measure for objectively detecting periods characterized by the lowest and the highest mental fatigue. Additional physiological metrics, such as ocular activity, heart rate variability, and skin conductance, were collected to provide a comprehensive characterization of the fatigued state. Behavioural data, including driving patterns and facial expressions, were also recorded to understand the broader implications of fatigue on driver performance.

Figure 3: Experimental setup during the realistic driving performed for C2 experiments. On the left, a picture from the experiments performed in Italy involving van drivers. On the right, a picture from experiments performed in Spain involving truck drivers.

The primary aim of C2 was to collect supplementary data on fatigued driving within a realistic environment. This phase sought to identify and validate the parameters, among highlighted during C1, most sensitive to fatigue, which would be instrumental in developing a generalized model for fatigue detection. By analysing data from naturalistic driving scenarios, the project aimed to ensure that the fatigue detection model would be both accurate and applicable in real-world settings.

Data collection during C2 involved a subset of participants from C1 (n = 19), allowing for a controlled yet realistic examination of fatigue-related parameters. The choice of recruiting a subset of C1 participants was performed to minimize the risks associated with fatigued driving while still providing a robust and representative data set. The outcomes of this phase included a refined list of driving and neurophysiological parameters that demonstrated sensitivity to fatigue. These parameters were crucial for informing the development of the AI model intended to detect fatigue, ensuring that the model was grounded in both controlled and real-world data. From C2 tests, a set of neurophysiological and driving parameters (respectively Table 4 and Table 5) were selected. Unlike C1, here the top ranked features match partially including some important ones like accelerator pedal position and speed. Please refer to Table 4 for a description of the parameters sensitive to fatigue, as emerged from C2 tests also. In respect to C1 tests, environmental factors concurring to fatigue could not be investigated during realistic driving because of a malfunction in the device capturing environmental data which resulted in the impossibility of gathering reliable data. As happened during C1 data analysis, the facial expressions of drivers could not be investigated since no threshold value for target measures was provided by the third-party company developing the analysis software.

Table 4: List of neurophysiological parameters sensitive to fatigue as highlighted during realistic driving (C2).

Neurophysiological Parameters	Description	Fatigue Effect
EBR	Blink frequency	Increase
EBD	Blink duration	Increase
EBA	Blink amplitude	-
HR	Heart rate	Increase
HRV	HR variability	-
SCL	Sweating	-

Table 5: List of vehicular parameters sensitive to fatigue as highlighted during simulated driving in Italy (C2.1) and Spain (C2.2), in a decreasing order of relevance.

Vehicular Parameters	Rank from C2.1	Rank from C2.2
Accelerator_pos_e	1	-
BrakePedalPosition	-	1
LateralAcceleration	-	2
Accelerator_pos_d	2	4
Value_throttle_pos	3	-
Value_speed	4	3
Value_acc_y	5	7

The findings from C2 were propaedeutic for the subsequent phases of the FitDrive project. By validating the parameters identified in the simulated environment and confirming their relevance in naturalistic settings, C2 provided a critical bridge between the initial experimental design and the development of a generalized fatigue detection model. This model would later be personalized in Cycles 3, where additional data would be collected to tailor the system to individual drivers, enhancing its accuracy and effectiveness in diverse driving scenarios. C2 represented a crucial step in transitioning from controlled experimental conditions to real-world applications. The data collected and the insights gained during this phase were instrumental in refining the parameters for fatigue detection and ensuring the feasibility and reliability of the proposed monitoring framework in naturalistic driving environments.

3.3. Cycle C3 – Individual Profiling

With C3 the FitDrive project implemented the fatigue detection framework from a generalized fatigue detection model to a personalized, user-specific system. This phase was designed to refine the previously developed framework by incorporating individual driving behaviour and physiological responses, ensuring that the model could adapt to specific users rather than relying solely on generalized patterns. The tests were conducted in three different locations: Italy, where van drivers participated, and Spain and Ireland, where truck drivers were involved. The main objective of this phase was to gather a large amount of individual data to train the model in recognizing individual driving styles. In the following cycle, C4, the model was then tested in its ability to recognize a specific driver based on their driving style (detected through driving parameters) and its physiological response. Also, the system has been designed to detect eventual deviation from the user's usual driving style, possibly addressing the cause of this

deviation as due to fatigue or other investigated factors. These included neurodegenerative disease known to impact on driving behaviour.

To achieve this, a new dataset was collected. It was focused on the naturalistic driving behaviour of professional drivers. Unlike the controlled settings of the previous cycles, this phase aimed to capture real-world driving conditions, including variations in workload, road types, and external influences. Participants were monitored throughout their daily work shifts, for approximately eight hours per day over a span of approximately 20 days, on average. This prolonged observation period allowed for the collection of comprehensive data reflecting spontaneous driving behaviours, eventual spontaneous fatigue occurrence, and potential adaptive strategies employed by drivers. They were involved 10 participants in Italy, 3 in Ireland and 3 in Spain.

The monitoring process was based on the key fatigue-sensitive parameters identified in the previous experimental phases (C1 and C2), ensuring consistency in data collection. These parameters included neurophysiological activation in terms of heart activity, and driving performance (selected parameters). By tracking these elements under real working conditions, the goal was to enhance the model's ability to recognize an individual driver, and establish a baseline for their usual driving behaviour.

The primary outcome of C3 was a large dataset, which was used to adapt the generalized fatigue detection model into a user-specific framework. This enhanced model became capable of recognizing individual "usual" driving style and detecting anomalies, that is deviations of driving parameters from the "usual" model. Such anomalies could then be classified as potential indicators of fatigue or other altering conditions, allowing for a more precise and personalized approach to fatigue monitoring. In our case, it is possible to assume that deviations from usual driving behaviour are linked to fatigue since the model has been built with parameters, properly weighted, that in previous steps (C1 and C2) have been demonstrated to be strictly related to fatigue. This step was crucial for increasing the accuracy and applicability of the FitDrive system, ensuring that it could provide tailored fatigue detection and intervention strategies.

Figure 4: Driving pattern of a participant driver in C3.1 tests during evening on a single day and a road segment with 100 km/h speed limit. The red dots identified the segments recognized as

“unusual” driving style. The average speed was not different from the speed generally adopted by the same driver on that segment, demonstrating that the “unusual” classification was not due to other external variables (e.g. traffic jam) but likely to an altered driving style. This picture is taken from D3.2.

Overall, C3 played a fundamental role in advancing the FitDrive framework from a general detection system to a personalized, driver-specific monitoring tool.

In fact, the data collected in C3 have been used to develop the individual models of “usual” driving behaviour that will be then employed in C4 to test the capability of the FitDrive system in detecting deviations from usual behaviour, i.e. altered driving conditions, and its causes (fatigue or other causes like drugs or neurocognitive diseases) on the same participants, thus simulating the calibration/learning phase of the system in a real application. It must be noted that the system was trained with data coming only from straight lanes, identified through GPS, filtering out all the vehicular parameters collected for examples in a roundabout or while turning.

3.4. Cycle C4 – FitDrive Framework Test

Cycle 4 (C4) marked the final phase of the FitDrive project, serving as the validation stage for the developed “fitness to drive” detection framework, i.e. the ability of the system in detecting an altered driving behaviour and its most probable cause, with a focus on fatigue, and other two simulated impairments, specifically drugs and neurocognitive diseases. The core objective of this phase was to test the system’s ability to assess drivers’ fitness to drive under various conditions. As a direct continuation of C3, the same professional drivers who participated in the previous phase were recruited, ensuring consistency in the dataset and enabling a reliable comparison of driving behaviours.

The primary goal of C4 was to evaluate the model’s ability to detect anomalies in driving patterns because of fatigue, also differentiating them from variations caused by other causes such as neurodegenerative conditions and or drug-induced impairments. To achieve this, participants were instructed on how to simulate each of these altered driving states, providing controlled examples for model validation.

Unlike C3, which was conducted in real-world driving conditions, C4 was performed in a controlled environment. This decision was made to ensure safety, as participants were explicitly asked to drive abnormally to test the system’s ability to detect deviations. The controlled setting allowed for the systematic introduction of specific driving alterations while maintaining a safe testing protocol.

Participants completed two types of driving sessions. The first consisted of driving naturally for half an hour along a ‘circuit’ identified for the test. The second involved deliberately altered driving behaviours, mimicking the effects of fatigue, neurodegenerative disorders, or drug influence. This approach enabled the FitDrive system to be tested on its ability to correctly identify impaired driving and attribute it to the appropriate underlying cause. By comparing

these sessions with the data collected during C3, the system’s capacity to recognize individual drivers based on their characteristic driving style and physiological responses was assessed.

The fatigue-related alteration of the driving behaviour was designed based on the evidence from C1 and C2, while the other two ways of altering the driving behaviour (neurocognitive disease and drugs) were designed with evidence coming from scientific literature. Here below it is provided a table highlighting the performance of the system in recognizing and ‘labelling’ the altered driving conditions.

Table 6: Overview of the classification performance of the FitDrive system in recognizing usual and unusual driving behaviours, and its probable impairment causing deviation from normal behaviour.

Location	Impairment simulated in C4	Average Accuracy (%)
Italy	Normal	100.00
	Fatigue	70.13
	Neuro-disease	75.83
	Drugs	93.185
Ireland	Normal	100.00
	Fatigue	73.29
	Neuro-disease	84.19
Spain	Normal	100.00
	Fatigue	63.00
	Neuro-disease	88.34
	Drugs	77.63
All countries	Normal	100.00
	Fatigue	67.48
	Neuro-disease	82.78
	Drugs	85.40

It is possible to see how the system was able to:

- Recognize the normal driving behaviour with the highest accuracy (100%);
- Recognize deviations from normal driving behaviour and link them to its most probable cause (fatigue, drugs, neuro-disease) with high accuracies, on average ranging from 67% to 85%;
- Distinguish the different causes among them.

Overall, C4 served as the final and most critical step in validating the FitDrive framework. By systematically testing the system's recognition and anomaly detection capabilities, this phase ensured that the model was not only sensitive to fatigue but also capable of distinguishing it from other potential impairments. The insights gained from this stage solidified the readiness of the FitDrive system for real-world applications, supporting its potential implementation in professional driving environments.

4. Discussions

FitDrive project represents a significant advancement in driver fatigue detection and management technology, directly addressing the critical limitations of existing systems that have been introduced at the beginning of this document.

First of all, the project employed a data-driven and scientifically sound approach by which, by utilizing neurometric indicators based on EEG measurements, an objective ground truth was established for fatigue onset, enabling precise identification of driving parameters and circumstantial variables that correlate with the earliest stages of driver fatigue. In fact, as introduced, existing systems mainly recognize only pronounced manifestations of fatigue and drowsiness, making effective and proactive prevention actions impossible. This is due to the fact that, in absence of a reliable ground truth, the usual research approach consisted of asking the participants driving for a prolonged time and considering the last part of the driving task as representative of the highest level of experienced fatigue. This FitDrive neurophysiological foundation provides unprecedented accuracy in understanding the actual onset of fatigue rather than relying on theoretical assumptions or late-stage behavioural manifestations. In fact, this approach allowed to restrict, among the huge set of parameters made available by the vehicle and the environment, only those strictly related to the phenomenon. Other than a result, this should become a best practice for future developments in this sector. In fact, the current approach relies on analysing as many parameters as possible, to increase the probability of recognizing the target phenomena from their variations. However, in this way it would become difficult to distinguish between different causes, i.e. impairments. In fact, currently vehicles are equipped with systems able to detect fatigue, or inattention, or sleepiness, or drowsiness, or altered driving, or distraction, but all these "labels" are just different names given to a system by the different car manufacturers: actually, their systems are only able to recognize a deviation from a pre-defined 'normal' behaviour. There are no systems on the same vehicle, to date, able to distinguish the mentioned impairments among them. This is because the current systems used all the available parameters in an agnostic way. The FitDrive system demonstrates the possibility to achieve this ability.

Furthermore, the FitDrive implementation of machine learning models designed to establish individualized driver profiles constitutes a paradigm shift in fatigue detection methodology. These models can detect subtle variations in driving behaviour that may indicate early-stage fatigue, providing a personalized approach that accounts for inter-individual differences. Unlike current commercial systems that apply universal thresholds across all drivers, FitDrive's adaptive algorithms can continuously refine their understanding of each driver's unique behavioural patterns, significantly improving detection sensitivity while reducing false alarms. This capability would be of high importance in the daily application, because besides the problems related to inaccuracy, another critical problem is the poor trust of the driver in these systems, due to the number of false alarms, potentially leading to ignore also true alarms, or even worse to disable the system.

5.Challenges & Limitations

The experimental activities also highlight some critical challenges that need more attention from the industrial sector, and/or more investigation from the scientific community. In particular:

- OBD/OBD-II, a standardized communication protocol that is not standardized. In fact, even if the communication protocol is standardized, each industry/vehicle manufacturer can make available different parameters or, in any case, with different format and characteristics (e.g. sampling frequency). Apart its effects on the project activities, imposing to restrict the use to specific vehicles, this is a serious limitation to develop generic safety systems that do not depend on the specific vehicle manufacturer.
- Awareness of models training time: the FitDrive project, thanks to its very robust and multimodal data-driven approach, has been able to achieve the important milestone of unsupervised learning for building individual models. However, the data amount, that depends on the driving time, has been set on 20 days of data recording. On one hand, it should be investigated how much time is needed to have a first version of individual models accurate enough to be reliable. On the other hand, probably the driver should be made aware of this process, to use the system appropriately.
- Limitation to straight lines. To reduce the “noise” on the measurements, given also the limited number of participants, all the collected data have been always filtered in order to leave out data related to situations in which the driver was not on a straight line. Even if it has not detailed into the document, this solution made the difference, allowing to achieve impressive accuracies that was not possible to achieve in a first step when the consortium was using all the data. This can be seen as a “limitation” for sure, but we have to take into account that the systems equipping the current vehicles are much more limited. For example, the ATTENTION ASSIST system by Mercedes-Benz, one of the most advanced currently available, has the following limitations (*Funzionamento dell’ATTENTION ASSIST con rilevamento dei colpi di sonno | EQS Elettrico Berlina marzo 2022 V297 MBUX | Manuale d’uso e manutenzione, s.d.*): it works after 30 minutes of travel, it works between 60 and 200 km/h, it works only if the road pavement is in a good state, it does not work in case of strong wind, it does not work in case of “sport” driving style (high speed curves or high accelerations), it does not work in case of frequent changes of speed and lanes, and in addition it does not work in any case if the face of the driver is not fully visible (e.g. because of sunglasses or external light). That means that also the current systems are strongly limited, therefore the FitDrive system, despite this limitation, is still forefront with respect to current solutions.

Anyhow, these challenges can be considered outcomes of the project as well, shading the lights on future priorities and lines of investigation.

6. Conclusions

Despite several technical challenges encountered throughout the project (as detailed in previous deliverables), the tests were successfully conducted, providing valuable insights into drivers' fatigue detection and fitness to drive. In this scenario, the FitDrive project represents firstly a significant advancement in driver fatigue detection technology, directly addressing the critical limitations of existing systems. By utilizing neurometric indicators based on EEG measurements, the project has established an objective ground truth for fatigue onset, enabling precise identification of driving parameters and circumstantial variables that correlate with the earliest stages of driver fatigue. This neurophysiological foundation provides unprecedented accuracy in understanding the actual onset of fatigue rather than relying on theoretical assumptions or late-stage behavioural manifestations.

Furthermore, the FitDrive implementation of machine learning models designed to establish individualized driver profiles constitutes a paradigm shift in fatigue detection methodology. These models can detect subtle variations in driving behaviour that may indicate early-stage fatigue, providing a personalized approach that accounts for inter-individual differences. Unlike current commercial systems that apply universal thresholds across all drivers, FitDrive's adaptive algorithms can continuously refine their understanding of each driver's unique behavioural patterns, significantly improving detection sensitivity while reducing false alarms.

Thank to this scientifically sound approach, the FitDrive system has been demonstrated to be able to recognize also impairing conditions other than fatigue, such as drugs and neurocognitive disease, demonstrating the possibility of assessing the overall "fitness to drive" of a driver, by detecting eventual deviations from its own usual behaviour and recognizing the most probable cause.

This advancement toward early detection capabilities addresses perhaps the most critical limitation of existing technologies - their inability to recognize fatigue and other altered conditions before they reach dangerous levels. By identifying the subtle, early indicators of fatigue onset, FitDrive enables preventive interventions at a stage when corrective actions are most effective and least disruptive. This proactive approach represents a substantial improvement over reactive systems that only activate once fatigue, or other impairing conditions, have already significantly altered driving performance. The combination of neurometrically-validated parameters, personalized profiling, and early detection, positions FitDrive as a transformative technology with the potential to substantially reduce fatigue-related accidents and enhance road safety beyond what current systems can achieve, potentially transforming traditional reactive warning systems into proactive fatigue management tools.

7. Bibliography

- Dawson, D., Reynolds, A. C., Van Dongen, H. P. A., & Thomas, M. J. W. (2018). Determining the likelihood that fatigue was present in a road accident: A theoretical review and suggested accident taxonomy. *Sleep Medicine Reviews*, 42, 202–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smr.2018.08.006>
- de Winkel, K. N., & Christoph, M. (2025). Rethinking Advanced Driver Assistance System taxonomies: A framework and inventory of real-world safety performance. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 29, 101336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2025.101336>
- Di Flumeri, G., Ronca, V., Giorgi, A., Vozzi, A., Aricò, P., Sciaraffa, N., Zeng, H., Dai, G., Kong, W., Babiloni, F., & Borghini, G. (2022). EEG-Based Index for Timely Detecting User's Drowsiness Occurrence in Automotive Applications. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 16. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fnhum.2022.866118>
- Driver Fatigue and Distraction Monitoring System—Market, Report Size, Worth, Revenue, Growth, Industry Value, Share 2024.* (s.d.). Valuates Reports. Recuperato 14 marzo 2025, da <https://reports.valuates.com/market-reports/QYRE-Auto-39Z13875/global-driver-fatigue-and-distraction-monitoring-system>
- Funzionamento dell'ATTENTION ASSIST con rilevamento dei colpi di sonno | EQS Elettrico Berlina marzo 2022 V297 MBUX | Manuale d'uso e manutenzione.* (s.d.). Mercedes-Benz. Recuperato 14 marzo 2025, da <https://www.mercedes-benz.it/passengercars/services/manuals.html/eqs-berlina-2022-03-v297-mbox/attention-assist/funzionamento-dellattention-assist-con-rilevamento-dei-colpi-di-sonno>
- Giorgi, A., Borghini, G., Colaiuda, F., Menicocci, S., Ronca, V., Vozzi, A., Rossi, D., Aricò, P., Capotorto, R., Sportiello, S., Petrelli, M., Polidori, C., Varga, R., Van Gasteren, M., Babiloni, F., & Di Flumeri, G. (2024). Driving Fatigue Onset and Visual Attention: An Electroencephalography-Driven Analysis of Ocular Behavior in a Driving Simulation Task. *Behavioral Sciences*, 14(11), Articolo 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs14111090>
- Giorgi, A., Ronca, V., Vozzi, A., Aricò, P., Borghini, G., Capotorto, R., Tamborra, L., Simonetti, I., Sportiello, S., Petrelli, M., Polidori, C., Varga, R., van Gasteren, M., Barua, A., Ahmed, M. U., Babiloni, F., & Di Flumeri, G. (2023). Neurophysiological mental fatigue assessment for developing user-centered Artificial Intelligence as a solution for autonomous driving. *Frontiers in Neurobotics*, 17. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fnbot.2023.1240933>
- How do I use the Driver Alert System?* (s.d.). Recuperato 14 marzo 2025, da <https://www.ford.com/support/how-tos/ford-technology/driver-assist-features/how-do-i-use-the-driver-alert-system/>
- Mark. (2017, gennaio 26). Driver Fatigue Detection. *Miles Continental Volkswagen*. <https://www.milescontinental.co.nz/news/features/driver-fatigue-detection/>

- Martensson, H., Keelan, O., & Ahlström, C. (2018). Driver Sleepiness Classification Based on Physiological Data and Driving Performance From Real Road Driving. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems, PP*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2018.2814207>
- Phillips, R., Kecklund, G., Anund, A., & Sallinen, M. (2017). Fatigue in transport: A review of exposure, risks, checks and controls. *Transport Reviews*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2017.1349844>
- SWOV. (2019). Fatigue. *SWOV-Fact sheet, September 2019*.
- V40 Driver Alert Control (DAC) | Volvo Support EN-JO. (s.d.). Recuperato 14 marzo 2025, da https://www.volvocars.com/en-jo/support/car/v40/18w17/article/e345e4c9352538b6c0a801e800ea8794_1ecc3be8a7e748d0c0a801e80003fd2a_2e82f6fc0d1139c2c0a801e800329d4e/
- Zhang, C., Wu, X., Zheng, X., & Yu, S. (2019). Driver Drowsiness Detection Using Multi-Channel Second Order Blind Identifications. *IEEE Access, PP*, 1–1. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2891971>

